

A theoretical model for ufra control. The yield response to late sowing or transplanting in a field affected by ufra is a trade-off between two potential yield functions. Bangladesh.

changed to achieve this effect (e.g. by shifting to a variety that flowers earlier or by the use of pregerminated seed instead of dry seeding), the maximum yields associated with the two functions may not coincide. The base yield of the function Y'' , if the crop is sown at the usual time, may not be zero.

The boundary of the shaded area in the figure defines the yield response that may be achieved by use of the practice. If the functions Y' and Y'' overlap, there will be an interior solution for the optimum time of sowing or transplanting (t^*), which gives the maximum attainable yield (y^*). The precise location of the functions defining the trade-off will depend on the variety used, the management level, the initial inoculum level, and the flood pattern. The future development of ufra control strategies by postponing the time of sowing or transplanting must consider the conditions under which an interior solution is generated. The model does not take into account additional benefits realized only in successive years as the initial level of inoculum is progressively reduced. ■

Ripcord — a synthetic pyrethroid against rice tungro virus

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The possibility of controlling or minimizing incidence of tungro virus was tried by controlling the vector insect through the

Data on rice tungro virus incidence. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment ^a	Rice tungro (%)		Stunted unproductive population (%)
	60th DT	75th DT	
1. RS with FMC 35001 at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg a.i./ha on 20th DT	77	82	68
2. Treatment 1 + FS with FMC 35001 at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45th DT	79	82	74
3. Treatment 1 + FS with FMC 35001 at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25 th and 45 th DT	75	79	68
4. RS with Ripcord at 0.01% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg ai/ha on 20th DT	79	81	72
5. Treatment 4 + FS with Ripcord at 50 g ai/ha on 45 th DT	77	85	65
6. RS with Ripcord at 0.01% + 1% urea + FS with Ripcord at 50 g ai/ha on 25th and 45th DT	28	52	15
7. RS with carbofuran SP at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 ai/ha on 20th DT	77	84	66
8. Treatment 7 + FS with carbofuran SP at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45 th DT	72	84	66
9. RS with carbofuran SP at 0.04% + 1% urea + FS with carbofuran 50 SP at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25th and 45 th DT	52	70	38
10. RS with chlorpyrifos at 0.04% + 1% urea + RZP of carbofuran at 0.25 kg ai/ha on 20th DT	80	91	68
11. Treatment 10 + FS with chlorpyrifos at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 45th DT	75	84	64
12. RS with chlorpyrifos at 0.04% + 1% urea + FS with chlorpyrifos at 0.5 kg ai/ha on 25th and 45th DT	76	82	64
13. Control	96	98	81
CD (P-0.05%)	6.8	8.9	5.4

^aRS = root soaking, RZP = root-zone placement, FS = foliar spray, DT = day(s) after transplanting.

following insecticides: carbofuran 3% G, carbofuran 50% SP, FMC 35001 (carbo-sulphan) 24% EC, Ripcord (cypermethrin-synthetic pyrethroid) 5% EC, and Dursban (chlorpyrifos) 20% EC. Three methods of application were tried: root soaking, root-zone placement, and foliar spray. Tungro incidence was assessed on tungro-susceptible variety ADT31 60 and 75 days after transplanting (DT). At

harvest the nonproductive population stunted by tungro was also assessed.

Root soaking with Ripcord along with 1% urea followed by foliar spray with Ripcord on the 25th and 45th DT gave low tungro incidence (see table). The synthetic pyrethroid Ripcord can be effective in reducing tungro incidence if used as foliar spray from 10 to 15 DT 3 times at 10- to 15-day intervals. ■

Chemical control of Helminthosporiose of rice

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Helminthosporiose of rice, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, is widespread in Kerala; its incidence is severe during the rabi (Oct–Jan) cropping season.

A field experiment on chemical control of the disease was conducted at the Pattambi RRS in the 1977–78 kharif and

rabi seasons. Seven fungicides — edifenphos EC, zineb, mancozeb, captafol, copper oxychloride, Aureofungin sol, and IBP — were sprayed on plants of the susceptible variety Benibhog three times at 14-day intervals beginning at 30 days after transplanting. The disease incidence was recorded 10 days after the final spraying and graded using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Plants treated with zineb had the lowest disease index in both seasons and a corresponding increase in grain yield.

Control of helminthosporiose of rice. Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	1977-78 seasons			
		Kharif		Rabi	
		Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	53	1.9	57	1.3
Zineb	2.0 kg	49	2.0	53	1.4
Mancozeb	2.0 kg	54	1.9	56	1.4
Captafol	2.0 kg	55	1.8	59	1.3
Copper oxychloride	2.0 kg	53	1.8	58	1.3
Aureofungin sol	0.05 kg	56	1.9	58	1.3
IBP	1.0 liter	50	2.0	58	1.4
Control	-	59	1.7	67	1.2
CD (0.05)		n.s.	n.s.	6.71	0.114

Plants treated with mancozeb, edifenphos, and IBP were amply protected but did not give commensurate yield increases (see table). ■

Herbicides in plant disease control

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A field experiment during punja season (Oct—Feb) in cultivators' fields in Kuttanad area, Alleppey, Kerala, under the Operational Research Project, studied the influence of herbicides on sheath blight and sheath rot control. The average disease scores of sheath blight and sheath rot are given in the table.

Average scores of sheath blight and sheath rot with different herbicides. Kerala, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight score (0-9)	Sheath rot score (0-9)
2,4-D spray at 1 kg a.i./ha	2.30	2.40
2,4-D at 1 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	3.35	3.15
Weedon (18%), 5 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	2.81	2.93
Benthiocarb (Saturn) granules at 2 kg a.i./ha applied to soil	3.15	2.75
Foliar application of benthiocarb at 2 kg a.i./ha	1.50	1.98
Hand weeding (control)	3.20	2.65

Symptoms of ufra disease of deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Three symptom types are proposed for ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) as it occurs under Bangladesh field conditions. The

Results indicate that spraying the foliage with benthiocarb (Saturn) reduced sheath blight and sheath rot.

Weeding is a problem for rice cultivation in Kuttanad. Because of the high labor cost involved in mechanical weed control, most farmers use chemical weed control. The information obtained through the present trial indicates that benthiocarb (Saturn) has an additional advantage of controlling sheath blight and sheath rot. These diseases are severe in this locality. ■

symptoms are based on the extent of panicle emergence (see figure). In ufra 1, the panicle fails to emerge; in ufra 2 the panicle exhibits partial emergence; and in ufra 3, the panicle emerges properly, but the grain remains unfilled. The categories *thor* ufra and *pucca* ufra by Butler correspond approximately to ufra 1 and ufra 3, respectively, although ufra 1 includes all panicles that fail to emerge, whether or not they also exhibit the spiral distortion characteristic of severe attack. The newly proposed

The symptoms of ufra (left to right): ufra 1, ufra 2, and ufra 3. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.

symptom type, ufra 2, is intermediate between ufra 1 and ufra 3, but appears to be distinct. The proportion of panicles in a defined area classified as ufra 2 has been found useful as a disease index. ■

Components of yield loss from ufra

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) sometimes occurs in well-defined patches within a field in southern Bangladesh. At harvest the patches are often visible from a distance because stems bearing healthy panicles lodge whereas diseased stems, supporting empty heads, remain erect. There is a distinct gradient in disease intensity across a single field.

A field of this type, about 6.5 km west of Chandina in Comilla District, was selected in November 1978. Crop-cuts of 4 m² were made in different parts of the field: 3 where disease intensity was highest, 3 where it was moderate, and 3 where it was lowest.